

Reliability and Accuracy of Ultrasonographic Muscle Thickness Measurements: Evaluating Key Postural Stabilisers in Rehabilitation

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Keywords

ultrasonography-high-resolution imaging, postural muscle function, measurement reproducibility, musculoskeletal assessment, rehabilitation diagnostics

Abstract

Introduction: Ultrasonography (USG) is a widely recognised, non-invasive imaging technique extensively applied in musculoskeletal diagnostics. Its capacity to provide real-time visualisation of muscle structure and function underpins its utility in clinical practice and scientific research. Nevertheless, the reliability and accuracy of USG measurements remain pivotal concerns influencing its efficacy in muscle assessment.

Objective: The aim of this study is to evaluate the reliability and accuracy of USG-based muscle thickness measurements for four critical postural stabilisers: *longus colli*, *serratus anterior*, *transversus abdominis* and *multifidus*. These muscles play essential roles in postural stability due to their tonic characteristics, making them central to rehabilitation interventions.

Methods: Twenty healthy participants were recruited for this investigation. Muscle thickness of the four target muscles was assessed in a resting state using standardised USG protocols. Both intra- and inter-rater reliability were analysed using Intraclass Correlation Coefficients (ICC). Measurement precision was quantified through Standard Error of Measurement (SEM) and Minimal Detectable Change (MDC), ensuring a robust evaluation of reliability metrics.

Results: The analysis revealed excellent intra-rater reliability for all muscles, with ICC values ranging from 0.97 to 0.99. Inter-rater reliability was highest for the serratus anterior (ICC = 0.89-0.95) and transversus abdominis (ICC = 0.79-0.85), while moderate agreement was observed for the longus colli (ICC = 0.52-0.89). The transversus abdominis demonstrated the highest measurement precision, with the lowest Standard Error of Measurement (SEM = 0.79-1.05 mm) and Minimal Detectable Change (MDC = 2.19-2.91 mm). In contrast, the multifidus exhibited greater variability (SEM > 2.1 mm; MDC > 6.0 mm), reflecting the inherent challenges in ultrasonographic assessment of deep spinal musculature. Despite these differences, all assessed muscles achieved acceptable reliability levels, supporting the clinical utility of ultrasonography in rehabilitation monitoring.

Conclusion: Ultrasonography proves to be a reliable and precise modality for assessing muscle thickness in a resting state, particularly for the *transversus abdominis* and *serratus anterior*. These findings substantiate the utility of USG in evaluating key postural stabilisers within rehabilitation settings. Standardising measurement protocols and enhancing operator training are recommended to further optimise their application and ensure consistent results.

INTRODUCTION

Ultrasonography (US) is an innocuous and versatile imaging tool widely used in medical diagnostic applications, particularly, diagnosis of the musculoskeletal system¹. Due to its ability to produce real-time images of tissues², US enables ac-

curate evaluation of muscle structure, movement, and function, and therefore, remains an essential modality in clinical as well as scientific research. One of the most significant applications of US is to quantify muscle function in terms of muscle thickness. The accuracy and reliability of ultrasonographic measure-

ments are fundamental parameters determining their clinical utility. Accuracy is a measure of US to precisely reflect actual changes in muscle thickness, whereas reliability is a parameter declaring the degree of repeatability of results by different examiners (inter-rater reliability) or by the same examiner at differ-

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ent time intervals (intra-rater reliability)³. In this article, it is pointed out that standardisation of the test protocols, i.e. patient positioning, device settings and probe location, is a critical consideration for minimising errors and achieving lowered variability in results⁴.

The selection of the *longus colli*, *serratus anterior*, *transversus abdominis* and *multifidus* muscles as the targets for ultrasonographic analysis is based on their critical role in postural stability and their tonic nature. They have a high percentage of slow-twitch (type I) fibres, which enable sustained, resistance-to-fatigue activity, required for the generation and sustenance of upright posture⁵.

Longus colli, a deep cervical flexor, is an essential component in the stabilisation of the cervical spine. Its dysfunction has been associated with neck pain and postural deviance. According to Schomacher and Falla⁶, ultrasonographic assessment of its form and function is valuable in offering information that can be used in the rehabilitation of a patient with cervical dysfunction.

The *serratus anterior* enables scapular upward rotation and protraction, and also plays a key role in shoulder girdle mechanics. Huang et al.⁷ proved that US is a valid tool for the assessment of this muscle's structure and activation, making its use justified during the monitoring of scapular stability in clinical practice.

The *transversus abdominis* serves as a deep stabiliser of the trunk and as a corset, modulating intra-abdominal pressure and spinal stiffness. Its routine assessment via US has been suggested by Koppenhaver et al.³, particularly in programmes of low back pain core stabilisation.

The *multifidus* exhibits segmental stabilising function in the lumbar spine. Despite its deep anatomical location, its examination is possible using US, which offers a non-invasive way of monitoring structure and functional adaptation with rehabilitation^{8,9}. Teyhen et al.⁸ and Reeve & Dilley¹⁰ highlighted the utility as well as limitations of measuring this muscle using ultrasonography.

The role of ultrasonography in postural muscle assessment is also supported in current literature¹¹⁻¹⁴. González-Medina et al.¹⁵ used US to demonstrate delayed activation of the deep trunk muscles in patients with chronic low back pain. Macedo et al.¹⁶ confirmed US to be an effective modality for assessing lumbar *multifidus* morphology and quality within clinical settings. Wójcik et al.¹⁷ used M-mode ultrasonography to quantify postural responses of the lateral abdominal wall, with emphasis on asymmetrical activation of transversus abdominis. Li et al.¹⁸ provided evidence regarding differential recruitment of the abdominal muscles during core exercises, whereas Mongold et al.¹⁹ demonstrated age-related differences in postural muscle function as assessed with ultrasonography.

Despite such advances, the clinical usefulness of US for assessing muscle thickness continues to be partially limited by inter-examiner reliability and a lack of standardised measurement practices^{4,10}. Further, the reliability of US measurements in some stabilisers of posture, such as *longus colli* or *multifidus*, continues to require testing in more standard, reproducible conditions.

Whereas in previous research ultrasonographic assessment of the postural muscles has been included, no authors have simultaneously evaluated reliability and accuracy between various stabilisers in a systematic approach. The *longus colli* is also underrepresented in the literature despite its clinical relevance.

The objective of the present study is to determine intra- and inter-rater as well as test-retest reliability concerning the resting ultrasonographic determination of muscle thickness, with regard to the following muscles: *longus colli*, *serratus anterior*, *transversus abdominis* and *multifidus*, in a healthy population using standardised protocols².

METHODOLOGY

Study design

This prospective observational study was designed to assess the intra- and

inter-rater, as well as test-retest reliability of ultrasonographic muscle thickness measurements performed in resting conditions. Standardised measurement protocols and testing conditions were implemented to ensure maximum reproducibility of the results.

Study group

Participant characteristics:

- 20 healthy volunteers (10 male, 10 female);
- age range: 19-23 years;
- normal body mass index (BMI);
- no history of musculoskeletal or neurological dysfunctions.

Exclusion criteria:

- past musculoskeletal injuries or surgeries;
- neurological or systemic diseases affecting muscle function;
- contraindications to ultrasonographic assessment.

Study procedure

1. Participant recruitment:

All participants were informed about the objectives and procedures of the study and provided written informed consent prior to enrolment.

2. Preparation for examination:

Participants were examined in standardised, seated posture, with physiological spinal alignment, feet flat on the ground and their gaze directed forwards. The skin at each ultrasound probe site was cleaned and marked with a skin-safe marker to ensure precise and repeatable localisation.

3. Ultrasound measurement protocol:

- Measurement timing: All measurements were performed on the same day between 3:00 p.m. and 6:00 p.m. in a controlled laboratory environment at 24°C to minimise physiological variability.
- Ultrasound equipment: The Arietta 50 (Hitachi) ultrasound system, with a 7.5 MHz high-frequency linear transducer, was used. The imaging depth was set to 5 cm for all measurements.
- Examined muscles: *longus colli*, *serratus anterior*, *transversus abdominis*, and *multifidus*.

- Measurement conditions: Each muscle was assessed only at rest. No contraction-based measurements were performed.
4. Measurement organisation:
Three experienced physiotherapists, each with over three years of clinical practice and certified completion of a three-level musculoskeletal ultrasonography course (totalling over 100 hours of training), conducted the assessments. Each examiner independently performed three repeated measurements per muscle for each participant. The sequence of muscle assessment and examiners was randomised to minimise order effects.
5. Measurement timing:
Test–retest reliability was assessed based on two independent measurement sessions performed on the same day, separated by a 30-minute interval, during which the participant rested. The same examiner conducted both sessions for each participant.

Standardisation of ultrasonographic muscle measurement

1. Longus colli muscle:
- Probe placement: The transducer was placed ~4 cm above the clavicle, lateral to the trachea and oesophagus, aligned longitudinally with the cervical spine and tilted posteriorly to visualise the anterior vertebral body surface.
 - Participant position: Supine with head in neutral position and upper limbs resting comfortably along the sides⁶.
2. Serratus anterior muscle:
- Probe placement: The transducer was placed along the midaxillary line at the level of the manubrium, perpendicular to the ribs, to visualise the muscle overlying the rib cage.
 - Participant position: Supine, head in neutral, upper limb abducted to 60°^{9,15}.
3. Transversus abdominis muscle:
- Probe placement: Positioned midway between the anterior superior iliac spine and the inferior costal margin at the midaxillary line with transverse orientation.
 - Participant position: Supine and hips flexed to approximately 60°^{9,17}.

4. Multifidus muscle:
- Probe placement: Oriented longitudinally at the L5 spinous process, then moved laterally and tilted medially to visualise the muscle adjacent to the facet joint.
 - Participant position: Prone, relaxed, with neutral lumbar lordosis^{8,16}.

Data analysis

- Intra-rater reliability: calculated using Intraclass Correlation Coefficient (ICC (3,1)), based on three consecutive measurements by the same examiner.
- Inter-rater reliability: calculated using ICC (2,1) based on the mean of three measurements per examiner across all raters.
- Test-retest reliability: assessed by comparing data from two measurement sessions on the same day and by the same examiner.

Classification of ICC values was based on the criteria proposed by Koo and Li²⁰:

- ICC < 0.5 = poor reliability;
- 0.5 ≤ ICC < 0.75 = moderate reliability;
- 0.75 ≤ ICC < 0.9 = good reliability;
- ICC ≥ 0.9 = excellent reliability.

Additional statistical measures included:

- Coefficient of Variation (CV) – to quantify relative variability;
- Standard Error of Measurement (SEM) and Minimal Detectable Change (MDC) – to evaluate reproducibility;
- Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Limits of Agreement (LoA) – to assess measurement accuracy (via Bland-Altman analysis);
- Repeatability Coefficient (RC) – to determine the smallest change beyond measurement error;
- Pearson’s correlation coefficient – to explore linear relationships between repeated measurements;
- One-way ANOVA – to detect systematic differences between examiner measurements (without interpreting consistency).

All statistical analyses were conducted using IBM SPSS (version 23) and Python 3.8 (with NumPy, SciPy and Matplotlib libraries).

RESULTS

Descriptive statistics and measurement variability

The mean ultrasonographic muscle thickness values for each of the four examined muscles (*longus colli*, *serratus anterior*, *transversus abdominis* and *multifidus*) demonstrated general consistency across all three examiners. The *multifidus* muscle presented the greatest absolute thickness values (mean ~12 mm), while the *transversus abdominis* was the thinnest (mean ~4.6 mm).

The *multifidus* also exhibited the highest standard deviation (SD: 3.7–4.1 mm), suggesting greater variability in measurement. In contrast, the *transversus abdominis* demonstrated the lowest SD and the narrowest 95% confidence intervals (CI), indicating the highest measurement stability.

Reliability and reproducibility

Intra-rater reliability was found to be excellent across all muscles, with ICC(3,1) values ranging from 0.97 to 0.99. The *transversus abdominis* and *serratus anterior* muscles showed the highest consistency. Inter-rater reliability (ICC(2,1)) was good to excellent for most muscles, but moderate for the *longus colli* (ICC = 0.52 for Examiner 3) and *transversus abdominis* (ICC < 0.80).

The Standard Error of Measurement (SEM) and Minimal Detectable Change (MDC) values followed a similar trend: lowest for the *transversus abdominis* (SEM: ~0.79–1.05 mm, MDC: ~2.2–2.9 mm), and highest for *multifidus* (SEM > 2.1 mm, MDC > 6 mm). Coefficients of variation (CV) confirmed the lowest relative variability for *transversus abdominis* and the highest for *multifidus*.

Accuracy and agreement

Mean Absolute Error (MAE) values mirrored SEM results, with the lowest error observed for the *transversus abdominis* and the highest for the *multifidus*. Bland-Altman plots showed no significant bias, with mean differences close to zero for all muscles.

Table 1

Descriptive statistics of ultrasonographic measurements (mean, SD and 95% CI)						
Muscle	Examiner	Mean (mm)	Standard Deviation (SD)	95% CI (lower limit)	95% CI (upper limit)	
Longus colli	Examiner 1	8.46	3.07	7.67	9.25	
	Examiner 2	8.10	2.71	7.40	8.80	
	Examiner 3	8.11	1.99	7.60	8.63	
Serratus anterior	Examiner 1	6.54	2.89	5.79	7.29	
	Examiner 2	6.94	2.94	6.19	7.70	
	Examiner 3	6.91	3.03	6.13	7.70	
Transversus abdominis	Examiner 1	4.62	1.45	4.24	4.99	
	Examiner 2	4.64	1.35	4.29	4.99	
	Examiner 3	4.77	1.79	4.31	5.24	
Multifidus	Examiner 1	12.25	3.82	11.26	13.24	
	Examiner 2	12.31	4.07	11.26	13.36	
	Examiner 3	12.28	3.74	11.32	13.25	

Table 2

Summary of reliability and measurement error metrics						
Muscle	Examiner	ICC (2,1)	ICC (3,1)	SEM (mm)	MDC (mm)	CV (%)
Longus colli	1	0.8979	0.9930	1.80	4.99	~36.3
	2	0.8490	0.9998	1.59	4.41	~33.2
	3	0.5244	0.9803	1.16	3.21	~25.2
Serratus anterior	1	0.8905	0.9924	1.70	4.70	~26.0
	2	0.8512	0.9914	1.72	4.75	~25.1
	3	0.9494	0.9993	1.78	4.93	~25.8
Transversus abdominis	1	0.8454	0.9994	0.85	2.36	~18.4
	2	0.8235	0.9963	0.79	2.19	~17.0
	3	0.7959	0.9959	1.05	2.91	~22.0
Multifidus	1	0.8907	0.9909	2.24	6.20	~18.3
	2	0.8788	0.9979	2.39	6.61	~19.2
	3	0.9081	0.9705	2.19	6.07	~17.8

Table 3

Accuracy and Limits of Agreement (LoA) (MAE and Bland-Altman results)					
Muscle	Examiner	MAE (mm)	Mean Diff (mm)	LoA lower (mm)	LoA upper (mm)
Longus colli	Examiner 1	1.95	-2.66	-6.01	6.01
	Examiner 2	1.78	2.96	-5.31	5.31
	Examiner 3	1.54	5.77	-3.87	3.87
Serratus anterior	Examiner 1	2.23	2.52	-5.66	5.66
	Examiner 2	2.41	8.88	-5.75	5.75
	Examiner 3	2.44	1.92	-5.94	5.94
Transversus abdominis	Examiner 1	1.05	4.14	-2.85	2.85
	Examiner 2	1.07	-3.77	-2.65	2.65
	Examiner 3	1.39	1.48	-3.51	3.51
Multifidus	Examiner 1	2.82	-5.33	-7.48	7.48
	Examiner 2	2.93	2.37	-7.97	7.97
	Examiner 3	2.55	3.85	-7.33	7.33

Table 4

Repeatability, correlation and ANOVA summary					
Muscle	Examiner	RC (mm)	Pearson's r	F-value	p-value
Longus colli	Examiner 1	8.5	0.0149	0.3581	0.6995
	Examiner 2	7.51	0.0166	0.3581	0.6995
	Examiner 3	5.47	0.1538	0.3581	0.6995
Serratus anterior	Examiner 1	8.01	-0.0044	0.3454	0.7084
	Examiner 2	8.13	-0.0241	0.3454	0.7084
	Examiner 3	8.4	-0.0078	0.3454	0.7084
Transversus abdominis	Examiner 1	4.02	-0.1914	0.1765	0.8383
	Examiner 2	3.74	-0.4022	0.1765	0.8383
	Examiner 3	4.97	-0.3158	0.1765	0.8383
Multifidus	Examiner 1	10.57	0.3688	0.004	0.996
	Examiner 2	11.27	0.3331	0.004	0.996
	Examiner 3	10.37	0.3919	0.004	0.996

The narrowest Limits of Agreement (LoA) were found for the *transversus abdominis*, indicating the most stable measurements. In contrast, the *multifidus* had the widest LoA ranges.

Additional statistical tests

Repeatability Coefficient (RC) values further confirmed the superior consistency of *transversus abdominis* measurements and the relatively high variability of *multifidus*.

Pearson's correlation coefficients (r) were at a low level across all muscles ($r < 0.4$), suggesting limited linear correlation in repeated measures. This may be attributed to low between-subject variability or non-linear distribution of measurement differences, which makes correlation analysis less suitable for this type of reliability testing.

ANOVA results revealed no statistically significant differences between examiner measurements for any of the muscles ($p > 0.05$), confirming the absence of systematic bias among raters. However, as ANOVA does not allow to evaluate reliability or consistency per se, no conclusions were drawn regarding measurement agreement based on these values.

DISCUSSION

In this study, higher intra- and inter-rater reliability was found for the *transversus abdominis* and *serratus anterior* muscles, and greater variability for the *longus colli* and *multifidus* muscles. These findings justify the use of ultrasonography (US) in clinical settings to measure postural stabilisers, and also to introduce muscle-specificity and examiner experience as requirements.

Reliability was highest in *transversus abdominis*, with intra-rater ICC measurements of 0.99 and small SEM and MDC values (SEM = 0.79–1.05 mm; MDC = 2.19–2.91 mm). The findings are in accordance with those obtained in previous research, e.g. Koppenhaver et al.³, who obtained *transversus abdominis* ICC values between 0.87 and 0.94 on an identical protocol. Likewise, Wójcik et al.¹⁷ offered stable activation patterns of this muscle using M-mode ultrasonography. Li et al.¹⁸ also demonstrated that this muscle shows expected activation patterns in various core stabilisation exercises, thereby establishing its utility in clinical monitoring.

The *serratus anterior* also exhibited satisfactory parameters of reliability, namely inter-rater agreement (ICC = 0.89–0.95), verifying its use for the evaluation of scapular motion. These results are consistent with those obtained by Huang et al.⁷, who determined the reproducibility of US to measure *serratus anterior* function. With the muscle superficial and with evident anatomical limits, it is particularly vulnerable to even ultrasonographic visibility.

In contrast, measuring the *multifidus muscle* was challenging with higher SEM and MDC values and highest Limits of Agreement (LoA). Similar findings were described by Teyhen et al.⁸, who included mention of variability in measurement due to the deep anatomical positioning and layering of paraspinal musculature. Macedo et al.¹⁶ emphasized operator experience as being key to reducing variability for evaluating *multifidus*, particularly among patients with low back pain. Reeve and Dilley¹⁰ also suggested that sonographic assessment of the muscle depends on trainer status and on patient positioning.

The *longus colli* also revealed moderate inter-rater reliability with ICC values as low as 0.52 in the data from one examiner. Although its functional relevance to stabilisation of the cervix is certain⁶, the muscle's deep location and proximity to the oesophagus and trachea are limitations to ultrasonographic imaging. Schomacher and Falla⁶ have already proven that consistent placement of the probe and regulated respiration are fundamental for accurate imaging.

Significantly, this study is one of the first in which four postural stabilisers were systematically assessed – over different body regions – using a unified measurement and analysis protocol. This integrated approach not only allows for increased comparison of measurement properties across muscles, but it also provides

an operational model for implementing US in multi-disciplinary rehabilitation practice.

Although in this study the reported measurement reliability values were generally good in terms of their magnitude, their interpretation should consider the context of measurement error as well as clinical utility. For instance, whereas a statistically high ICC of > 0.9, a very high MDC may be limiting in terms of its clinical utility in identifying modest clinical changes. The low Pearson correlation coefficients (<0.4) reported in this work reflect the limited application of correlations in repeated-measure contexts and underscore the need for multi-metric reliability measurement.

In subsequent studies, these observations must be confirmed in symptomatic populations and across more heterogeneous demographic groups, including older adults and individuals with musculoskeletal disability. The addition of advanced US modalities, including elastography or dynamic feedback systems, may also reduce variability in harder-to-image muscles, such as the *multifidus* or *longus colli*. Lastly, ongoing optimisation of standardising US protocols and training programmes for examiners must be maintained to enable consistency and reliability within both clinical and research settings.

Study limitations

Despite providing useful information, this study is not without limitation. The relatively modest sample size can limit generalisability of the results and diminish statistical power to detect minor differences between subgroups. Increasing the number of participants in subsequent studies may improve statistical testing power and facilitate stratified measurement on the basis of parameters such as age, sex and physical activity status, which may influence muscle thickness and measurement variation.

In addition, the inter- and intra-rater variability found— particularly in muscles such as the *longus colli* and *multifidus* – suggests that examiner experience is a predominant factor determining ultrasonographic measurement reliability. It is recommended to

standardise the procedure in measurements and incorporate formal training programmes for examiners to minimise operator-dependent variability and achieve maximum reproducibility in forthcoming studies.

CONCLUSIONS

This study allows to confirm that ultrasonographic measures of resting muscle thickness have good to excellent intra- and inter-rater reliability for the majority of the key postural stabilizers, particularly the *transversus abdominis* and *serratus anterior*. The results highlight the clinical utility of ultrasonography in monitoring trunk and scapular stabilisers in rehabilitation. However, the *multifidus* and *longus colli* muscles showed greater variability of measurements, pointing out the need for further methodological standardisation and examiner training in an attempt to improve reproducibility. The findings support the application of standardised ultrasonographic protocols in both clinical practice and future research.

Author declarations

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